

PHYSICAL AND CHEMICAL QUALITY INDICATORS OF DRINKING PASTEURIZED MILK OF UKRAINIAN PRODUCERS**Zadorozhna O.,***Pavlo Tychyna Uman State Pedagogical University;
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Pavlo Tychyna Uman State Pedagogical University***ABSTRACT**

A healthy lifestyle involves high-quality and complete nutrition. Milk and dairy products have a high specific weight in the diet of the population of Ukraine. We conducted a study of the quality of drinking pasteurized milk of Ukrainian producers, which are the most popular in the domestic market.

Keywords: chemical composition, drinking milk, dry residue, titrated acidity.

Formulation of the problem. Milk and dairy products are of great importance for the organization of healthy and high-quality nutrition of the population. Milk is a complete and useful food product, containing almost the complete composition of nutrients necessary for the human body, which are required for normal life. The biological and nutritional value of milk lies in the optimal balance of components, which is easily absorbed by the human body. All nutrients in milk (proteins, fats, carbohydrates, minerals, microelements, vitamins, enzymes) are contained in such a ratio that meets human needs. However, only high-quality milk and dairy products have valuable properties [1-3].

Due to violations of production processes and non-compliance with sanitary and hygienic conditions, milk and dairy products lose their nutritional value and become dangerous for the health of consumers. The quality of milk is characterized by its physico-chemical, biological and technological properties. Therefore, it is necessary to study and control the quality of dairy products.

Methods of research. The density of drinking pasteurized milk was determined by the hydrometric method. Acidity of milk - by titrametric method. The mass fraction of fat - by the acid method. The mass fraction of dry residue and moisture was determined by the drying method.

Analysis of recent research and publications. Milk is a product of the normal secretion of a cow's mammary gland. From the physicochemical point of view, milk is a complex polydisperse system in which the dispersion medium is water, and the dispersed phase is substances in molecular, colloidal, and emulsion states. Milk sugar and mineral salts form molecular and ionic solutions. Proteins are in a dissolved (albumin and globulin) and colloidal (casein) state, milk fat is in the form of an emulsion. Milk contains more than 200 different mineral and organic substances. Cow's milk is also a source of phosphorus and calcium, which actually determines its important role in the nutrition of children - because at an early age there is active growth of the skeleton and teeth. This valuable

product contains manganese, iron, and cobalt, which, together with vitamin B12, play an important role in hematopoietic processes. The carbohydrate component of milk is presented in the form of lactose - milk sugar, its approximate amount is up to 5%. Lactose is a source of energy, contributes to the efficient operation of many internal organs - liver, heart, kidneys [4-6].

Lactose is also a necessary element for improving the assimilation of calcium in the body. Experts have proven the fact that lactose contributes to the formation of melanin, a special substance that plays an important role in the structure of human brain tissue.

A healthy lifestyle involves quality nutrition. Milk and dairy products traditionally have a fairly high specific weight in the diet of the population of Ukraine.

It is known that depending on the heat treatment, pasteurized milk and sterilized milk are distinguished. There are several types of pasteurized milk: pasteurized milk of different fat content (1.0; 1.5; 2.0; 2.5; 3.2; 3.5; 6.0%) and skim milk; melted; protein; vitaminized; enriched with various fillers (malted milk; milk with cocoa; milk with coffee; milk for cocktails) [7-10].

Pasteurized milk of different fat content can be produced by the normalization method of natural milk, as well as by the method of reconstitution of dry milk. Normalization of milk is carried out before its pasteurization and homogenization by mixing fatty milk with cream or with skimmed milk. Skimmed milk and cream are obtained by separating milk using special equipment - separators. Separation is the process of dividing milk under the action of centrifugal force into cream (fat phase of milk) and skimmed milk (plasma of milk).

Milk with increased fat differs from other types of pasteurized milk only in increased fat, and therefore, increased calories. It can be recommended to those who need high-calorie nutrition. For drinking milk, preference should be given to ordinary pasteurized milk with a fat content of 2.5 or 3.2%, since the ratio of protein substances and fats is more favorable in it than in high-fat milk [11-15].

The purpose of the work - research of physico-chemical parameters of drinking pasteurized milk

Results.

For the study, we chose the five most popular domestic milk producers represented on the Ukrainian market:

- «Selyanske»

- "Bila Liniya"
- "Farm"
- "Yagotynske"
- "Molokia"

Table 1

№	Manufacturer	Brand	Name
1	Lustdorf LLC, Illintsi, Vinnytsia region.	«Selyanske»	
2	Bilotserkivskyi LLC dairy plant", Bila Tserkva, Kyivska region	"Bila Liniya"	
3	LLC "TERRAFOOD" PJSC "Bilotserkivsky Dairy Plant"	"Farm"	
4	TDV "YAHOTYNSKY OIL PLANT"	"Yagotynske"	
5	PJSC "Ternopil milk factory"	"Molokia"	

Fig. 1. Organoleptic assessment of milk quality.

According to organoleptic indicators, all samples fully meet the requirements of DSTU 2661:2010. Tasters noted sample number 3 (Farm) as the best.

Fig. 2. Titrated acidity, T

The freshness of all types of drinking milk is indicated by its acidity, it should not exceed 21'T. In the studied samples, the index of titrated acidity is within the requirements of DSTU, but the sample of TM "Selyanske" has the highest value.

Fig. 3. Dry residue, %

The highest content of dry milk residue is determined in the milk of TM "Farm" - 12.4%. This indicator is influenced by many factors: the age of the animals, the quality of the feed, but the degree of breeding also affects it. A reduced content of solids, especially against the background of a low fat content, clearly indicates the falsification of milk.

Fig. 4. Mass fraction of fat, %

The price of milk directly depends on the mass fraction of fat in it. Milk fat is expensive, and due to its easy assimilation (97%) and high content of biologically active substances, it is one of the most valuable dietary fats. Falsification of milk due to a decrease in its fat content is one of the most widespread. After examining the fat content in the selected milk samples, it was established that, mainly, it corresponds to the specified norm

Fig. 3. Density, kg/m³

Milk is characterized by certain stable physical properties: density, viscosity, surface tension, freezing point, boiling point, osmotic pressure, electrical conductivity, specific heat capacity, optical properties. During adulteration, the quality of milk, as a single physicochemical system, changes significantly, which is explained by the properties of the components. One of the most important physical indicators of milk, which can prove its good quality or falsification, is density. The density of milk ranges from 1026 to 1031 kg/m³. If milk is diluted with water, the density decreases. In accordance with the requirements of DSTU 2661:2010, the density of the tested samples should be at least 1027 kg/m³. All samples except «Bila Liniya» milk meet these requirements

Conclusions. Cow's milk, which is characterized by high nutritional properties, is mainly used in human nutrition. They are determined by its chemical composition, digestibility, energy value, organoleptic indicators, use.

We investigated that almost all samples of drinking pasteurized milk met the standards according to organoleptic and physico-chemical parameters. The manufacturer of the trademark «Ferma» was recognized as the best sample according to all the investigated indicators

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